

**EMPLOYEE INVOLVEMENT TOWARDS KARUR
GOLDLINE EXPORTS PVT LTD, KARUR DISTRICT
TAMILNADU: ANALYTICAL STUDY**

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Abstract:

The Project has been done in Karur Goldline Exports Pvt Ltd. The title of the project is "A Study on Employee Involvement towards Karur Goldline Exports Pvt Ltd, Karur". The main objective of the study is to find out the employees engagement towards the organization. The collected data was analyzed by using relevant tools such as percentage analysis, chi-square test, paired comparison t-test were found related to employee and factor related to employees involvement in Karur Goldline Exports Pvt Ltd - Karur. The First Chapter deals with introduction, importance, statement of the problem, the scope, objectives, limitations and Research methodology. The Second Chapter deals with Review of literature. The Third chapter deals with the Complete Profile of Organization. The fourth chapter deals with the analysis and data interpretation. The fifth chapter reflects the thoughts of the researcher in the form of findings, suggestions and conclusions. Various supporting information have been incorporated for an easy understanding of the readers.

Introduction about Employee Involvement towards Karur Goldline Exports:

Employee involvement means that every employee is regarded as a unique human being, not just a cog in a machine, and each employee is involved in helping the organization meet its goals. Each employee's input is solicited and valued by his/her management. Employees and management recognize that each employee is involved in running the business. Employee involvement is creating an environment in which people have an impact on decisions and actions that affect their jobs. Employee involvement is not the goal nor is it a tool, as practiced in many organizations. Rather, it is a management and leadership philosophy about how people are most enabled to contribute to continuous improvement and the on-going success of their work organization. My bias, from working with people for 40+ years, is to involve people as much as possible in all aspects of work decisions and planning. This involvement increases ownership and commitment, retains your best employees, and fosters an environment in which people choose to be motivated and contributing. How to involve employees in decision making and continuous improvement activities is the strategic aspect of involvement and can include such methods as suggestion systems, manufacturing cells, work teams, continuous improvement meetings, Kaizen (continuous improvement) events, corrective action processes, and periodic discussions with the supervisor. Intrinsic to most employee involvement processes is training in team effectiveness, communication, and problem solving; the development of reward and recognition systems; and frequently, the sharing of gains made through employee involvement efforts.

Impacts of Employee Involvement in the Workplace:

The impacts of employee involvement to an organization have numerous positive and negative outcomes. Managers must determine the most effective employee involvement strategy(s) by specific having clear and concise organizational goals. Managers from different organization at all levels must work effectively with their employees to carry out specific responsibilities while showing some degree of independence to the employee; however some managers train their employees to accept various responsibilities and duties assigned to them. Walter and supports this by stating "some organization present their employees with rewards, acknowledgment and recognition for performing tasks effectively and with high standards" (Walter, 2005). Listed below are factors that have been outlined by relevant researchers, scientists and doctors in this field that are potential positive and negative impacts of Employee Involvement to all stakeholders within an organization.

Positive Impacts:

Teamwork: McKenna has argued that "employee involvement or participation in the decision making process gives every employee an opportunity to express their opinions, and to share their experience knowledge with other employees or employers" (McKenna, 2002). This would improve the relationship between a manager and the employee; while it encourages a feel of teamwork among other employees. Expressing various views

enables effective communication between co-workers, with each worker bringing individual strengths to a specific project or task and ultimately an increase in good teamwork and performance.

Employee Commitment: With the degree of employee involvement increasing in a number of organizations across the country, it is primarily due to and increase employee commitment to the company in which they are employed by. McKenna also says that "managers that actively involve employees in decision making, results in deeper commitments from the employee to organizational and job responsibilities, producing high levels of success for the manager and the organization overall" (McKenna, 2002).

Innovative and Creative Ideas: Heath field's text has expressed that an organizations customers benefit when companies seek employee input. Motivated senior employees that interact with customers or clients on a day to day basis often have more insight into what the customer wants from the organization, concerns and feedback. When a boss creates a workplace environment that encourages employees to collaborate creative, innovative and logical ideas through various meetings or discussions, get a clear grasp to what customers want (Heathfield, 2010)

Negative Impacts:

Manager-Employee Boundaries: Probst has stated through is findings, having high levels of employee involvement is a risk as the line of authority between the management level and employee level can blur (Probst, 2005). Managers may appreciate the value of employee involvement, however a disciplined structure with clear reporting responsibilities are vital to stability in organizations.

Miscommunication: Non-effective use of communication, inexperience and poor decision making skills is a major disadvantage with employee involvement. The more employees that have input and into managerial decision making tasks, higher levels of communication is essential to ensure that decisions are consistent across sectors of the workplace to ensure consistency.

Objectives of the Study:

- To identify general practices that organizations use to involvement and select employees.
- To determine which employee involvement are most effective.
- To study the employee performances and attitudes engage to the industry.
- To study the employee involvement practices in a well-established for baby wear product in the firm.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of the employee involvement.
- To find out the satisfaction levels of the employees with the current system.

Review of Literature:

- Verma. R, (2022) Employee Empowerment' means 'to give authority to the people'. Employee employment involves less hierarchical and gives the employees more liberty in their jobs. This facilitates them to make quick decisions and not wait for decisions to flow from their top managers. It is the act of enabling or authorizing an employee to think, take action, and control work and decision making in an self-governing or autonomous way. It is the state of mind when one feels that he is self-empowered to control one's own destiny
- Markos and Sridevi (2022) have stated that employee involvement is a strong predictor of positive organizational performance and clearly shows the two-way relationship between employer and employee compared to the three earlier constructs: employee commitment, job satisfaction, and organizational citizenship behavior. Employees who are engaged are emotionally attached to their organization and are highly involved in their job with a great deal of enthusiasm for the success of their employer, often going that extra mile beyond the contractual employment agreement. This study try to expresses the relationship between Employee empowerment and Employee performance.
- Abhijeet Singh Chauhan (2021) In the organizations molding the employees is a very tough task for the managers, in order to make the optimization in the employee's performance the managers try different methods, among these methods employee empowerment is one of them it means the delegation of authority and responsibility to the employees, as it is an important basis for improving the service quality and productivity of the organizations if employees are given importance, encouragement, priority and recognition for their work then it will create the feeling of belongingness in them accordingly their performance will also increase employee absenteeism will also reduce and they will work with full of their efficiency and effectiveness..
- Jalal Hanaysha (2021) Organizational commitment is one of the most widely researched topics in the field of organizational behaviour. The main objective of this study is to test the effects of work engagement, organizational learning, and work environment on organizational commitment in higher education sector. The findings indicated that employee involvement has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment. It was also found that work environment has a significant positive impact on organizational commitment. Finally, the outcomes of this study confirmed that organizational learning has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment. These findings provide useful insights and suggestions for the management in higher educational institutions to learn developing

organizational commitment among their employees by adopting effective human resource practices that could ultimately lead organizational competitiveness and increased performance.

- Catherine Bailey (2021) Securing high levels of employee involvement has become a dominant concern for HR practitioners globally, and a lucrative survey and consultancy industry has grown up around the topic. Despite significant parallel interest within the scholarly community, it is questionable whether research published in peer-reviewed journals has had any impact on the practice of engagement. The divergent perspectives of academics and practitioners on engagement are explored within the wider context of evidence-based management and the ‘rigor – relevance’ debate, alongside consideration of the risks of presupposing a simplified binary divide between the two communities. Some suggestions for strategies aimed at creating a stronger connection between the interests of practitioners and those of academics are proposed, whilst bearing in mind academia’s broader and more critical remit.
- Syed Talib Hussain (2020) Change is crucial for organizations in continuous growing and high competition in business environment. Different theories of change describe the effectiveness of modification of strategies, processes and structures for organizations. This study views the Lewin’s model as three steps process (unfreezing, movement and refreezing) for change in organization. Although this model sets a general steps to be followed, more information is considered to guide these steps in specific situations. This article is critically reviewed for change theories in different phases of organizational change. In this critical review the change management has constructive framework for managing the organizational change through different phases of the process.
- Stephan (2020) Preparing the organization’s overall performance to compete and reach its future goal in turbulence business environment is one of the management’s responsibility. The prior key to do is by improving the employee involvement within the organization, as we know that employee is the most crucial capital that can props the sustainability of an organization. This research tried to improve the employee involvement in PT Maju Sentosa. However, a negative association between intrinsic job satisfaction and turnover intention was not supported. The implications of these results for future research are also discussed.
- Maniam Kaliannan (2020) Employee involvement as an “engine” in talent management drive draws its resilience from the effectiveness of various environmental factors from within and outside an organization. Strategic employee involvement initiatives support organizational branding and reputation among employees. This paper explores the strengths and weaknesses of employee involvement strategies implemented by a telecommunications organization in Ghana. Quantitative research approach was adopted with completed responses. The findings reveal that the engagement strategies deployed by the organization has achieved level of satisfactory. However there are areas of improvement that can be established to integrate the talent management with overall organizational corporate strategies.

Research Design:

“A Research Design is the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with the economy in procedure”. The research design adopted for the studies is descriptive design. The researcher has to describe the present situation in order to know the behavior of the consumers. Hence descriptive research study is used. Descriptive research can only report what has happened and what is happening.

Research Methodology:

Research Methodology is a systematic way to solve a research problem; It includes various steps that are generally adopted by a researcher in studying the problem along with the logic behind them. The present study Employee Involvement towards Karur Goldline Exports Pvt Ltd at Karur

Method of Data Collection:

- Primary data
- Secondary data

Hypothesis of the Study:

- Null Hypothesis: There is no employee involvement in an organization.
- Alternative Hypothesis: There is employee involvement in an organization.

Statistical Tools Used:

The commonly used statistical tools for analysis of collected data are:

- Simple Percentage analysis
- Chi-square Analysis
- Correlation analysis

Scope of the Study:

- The study has planning for future reference and scope of scheduled prevents.

- The study has contempt in future reference to advantage resemble order.
- The study is focus each and every employee and their engage make an efficiency of skills and knowledge for future planning to awareness.
- The study must be safety for Employee engage to the right job.

Limitations of the Study:

- Time is the major constraint in collecting the data from the employees.
- The data collection is conducted only in Karur.
- Hence, utmost care is to be taken while generalizing the result.
- This study is confined to the employee’s details only.
- Some of the respondents are not responding for replay the schedule.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Their Opportunities for Their Growth

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Satisfied	67	67
Highly Satisfied	28	28
Dissatisfied	4	4
Highly Dissatisfied	1	1
Total	100	100

Source Data: Primary Data

Interpretation:

As per the above table it is clear that out of the 100 respondents, 67 percentage of the respondents are Satisfied, 28 percentage of the respondents are Highly Satisfied, 4 percentage of the respondents are Dissatisfied, 1 percentage of the respondents are Highly Dissatisfied.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Their Relationship with Colleagues

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	89.9	89.9
No	10.1	10.1
Total	100	100

Source Data: Primary Data

Interpretation:

As per the above table it is clear that out of the 100 respondents, 89.9 percentage of the Respondents are belong to Yes category, 10.1percentage of the respondents are belong to No category.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by their Satisfaction Level Related to Training

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Satisfied	18	18
Highly Satisfied	79	79
Dissatisfied	3	3
Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
Total	100	100

Source Data: Primary Data

Interpretation:

As per the above table it is clear that out of the 100 respondents, 18 percentage of the Respondents are Satisfied, 79 percentage of the respondents are Highly Satisfied, 3 percentage of the respondents are Dissatisfied, 0 percentage of the respondents are Highly Dissatisfied.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents by their Appreciation/Recognition of Employees

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Always	83	83
Sometimes	15	15
Never	2	2
Often	0	0
Total	100	100

Source Data: Primary Data

Interpretation:

As per the above table it is clear that out of the 100 respondents, 83 percentage of the respondents are belong to Always category,15 percentage of the respondents are belong to Sometimes category, 2 percentage of the respondents are belong to Never category, 0 percentage belong to Often Category.

Suggestions:

- Based on the study, the employees feel that the flow of information from top to bottom in the hierarchy is not timely and comprehensive. It is suggested that more transparency and timeliness is required in

the flow of communication within the organizations, which goes a long way in boosting the morale of the human resources of the organization.

- Organization shall organize special meetings/workshops to disseminate the value system and ethical fabric among their employees enabling them to understand the vision and mission.
- Very few employees feel that their ideas or work aren't being recognized / appreciated. So they can be encouraged by giving importance to their ideas
- Gap between managers and the employees should be reduced by raising the level of engagement. For example: by conducting extra co-curricular activities like social and cultural programs.
- Non-financial incentive plans could also be implemented; it could improve the productivity of the employees according to their performances.

Conclusion:

From the in-depth analysis on the data collected from the study conducted it is clearly observed that the employees of Karur Goldline Exports (P) Ltd Karur, very interestingly all the respondents are 'engaged' and only some of them are either 'not engaged' or 'actively disengaged'. Most of them are found to be happy and comfortable with the kind of recognition and rewards and motivation they get from the administration. In relation to the research itself, it was a positive aspect that so many employees were willing to come forward and be so honest in making suggestions. Based on the findings & the suggestions made for increasing the level of satisfaction further. If these are considered and implemented, there is no doubt that the employees will be more involved, satisfied and contribute further for the overall development of the organization.

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